

Blue-Cloud

Piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy

D5.4 Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholders Engagement Final Report, including events

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Lead Partner	TRUST-IT
Lead Author (Org)	Federico Drago (Trust-IT)
Contributing Author(s)	Sara Pittonet, Rita Meneses, Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)
Reviewers	Julia Vera (Seascape Belgium)
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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. OVERVIEW OF THE BLUE-CLOUD COMMUNITY	8
2. TARGETED PROMOTION OF BLUE-CLOUD KERS AND ASSETS VERSUS TARGET STAKEHOLDERS.....	10
2.1. VISIBILITY TOWARDS THE EOSC COMMUNITY.....	11
2.2. VISIBILITY TOWARDS THE DIGITAL OCEAN TWINNING COMMUNITY	14
2.3. VISIBILITY TOWARDS THE UN AND ATLANTIC COMMUNITIES	16
2.4. PROMOTION OF THE BLUE-CLOUD DATA DISCOVERY AND ACCESS SERVICE (DD&AS)	18
2.4.1. <i>Video interviews</i>	18
2.4.2. <i>EOSC in practice story</i>	19
2.4.3. <i>Posters and presentations</i>	20
2.5. TARGET PROMOTION OF THE BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT (VRE).....	22
2.5.3. <i>User survey with VRE users</i>	22
2.5.4. <i>Tutorial on the usage of the VRE</i>	23
2.5.5. <i>EOSC in practice story</i>	24
2.6. PROMOTION OF THE THEMATIC VIRTUAL LABS.....	24
2.6.1. <i>Blue-Cloud VLab Webinars</i>	24
2.6.2. <i>VLab Article series</i>	26
2.6.3. <i>Blue-Cloud use case on WEkEO</i>	27
2.6.4. <i>Interviews</i>	27
2.6.5. <i>VLab factsheets</i>	28
2.7. PROMOTION OF THE BLUE-CLOUD STRATEGIC ROADMAP 2030.....	29
2.7.1. <i>Support to the Roadmap open consultation</i>	29
2.7.2. <i>Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshops</i>	31
3. OUTREACH AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES M19-M42	33
3.1. BLUE-CLOUD PUBLIC WEBSITE	33
3.1.1. <i>Website evolution</i>	35
3.2. SOCIAL MEDIA	37
3.2.1. <i>Twitter</i>	37
3.2.2. <i>LinkedIn</i>	38
3.2.3. <i>YouTube</i>	40
3.3. ZENODO COMMUNITY	41
3.4. NEWSLETTERS	42
3.5. PRESS COVERAGE.....	44
3.6. SCIENTIFIC PAPERS	45
3.7. SPECIAL ISSUE JOURNAL.....	49
3.8. COMMUNICATION MATERIALS (DIGITAL AND PRINT)	50
3.9. HORIZON RESULTS BOOSTER ACTIVITY.....	51
4. EVENTS.....	52
4.1. BLUE-CLOUD WORKSHOPS.....	52
4.2. BLUE-CLOUD HACKATHON.....	54
4.3. BLUE-CLOUD FINAL CONFERENCE	55
4.4. BLUE-CLOUD AT THIRD-PARTY EVENTS.....	56
5. COVID-19 CONTINGENCY PLANS	62
6. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS TARGETS ACHIEVED	62
7. CONCLUSIONS	64

Table of Tables

Table 1 Blue-Cloud Community	8
Table 2 Blue-Cloud KERs and assets vs Blue-Cloud Stakeholders	10
Table 3 Blue-Cloud and AANChOR co-organised events	18
Table 4 Statistics from Blue-Cloud webinars	25
Table 5 The five articles dedicated to the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs	26
Table 6 Roadmap and policy workshops with ESEB	32
Table 7 Website KPIs.....	34
Table 8 Social Media KPIs	37
Table 9 Examples of popular followers on Twitter.....	38
Table 10 Blue-Cloud newsletters	44
Table 11 Examples of articles featured on third party websites	45
Table 12 Blue-Cloud communication materials by M41	51
Table 13 Blue-Cloud workshops	53
Table 14 Blue-Cloud presence at third-party events.....	62
Table 15 Target KPIs and achievements	63

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Countries of Blue-Cloud community database members	9
Figure 2 Stakeholder Categories in Blue-Cloud Database	9
Figure 3 Delivering for EOSC: Key Exploitable Results of the Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects (Summary report), Blue-Cloud Key Exploitable Results	13
Figure 4 Panel session during the workshop organised by Blue-Cloud at the EOSC Symposium 2022	14
Figure 5 Pierre Bahurel, Director General Mercator Ocean International, introducing the DTO Mission to mobilise strategic actors at the Digital Ocean Forum	15
Figure 6 A screenshot from the interview with Peter Pissierssens	17
Figure 7 The interview with Dick Schaap on the DD&AS.....	18
Figure 8 Shots from the interviews with data infrastructures representatives	19
Figure 9 EOSC In practice story “Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research”	20
Figure 10 Peter Thijsse presenting the DD&AS at OSFAIR 2021	21
Figure 11 Poster and slides presented at EGI 2022	21
Figure 12 Statistics on the purpose of Blue-Cloud usage in the user survey	22
Figure 13 Statistics on the functionalities thought as most useful in the user survey	23
Figure 14 Promotional visual for the five articles on Zenodo	27
Figure 15 Cover and one factsheet from the collection	29
Figure 16 Promotional image for the Roadmap Public Consultation (left) and promotion on social media (right)	30
Figure 17 Sample of the outcomes of the Roadmap survey run in the second open consultation phase.....	31
Figure 18 Cover of Roadmap Executive Summary.....	31
Figure 19 Blue-Cloud Policy Dialogue: Co-creating the Roadmap to 2030” branding	32
Figure 20 Blue-Cloud website homepage	33
Figure 21 Blue-Cloud website homepage first scroll with services	33

Figure 22 Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs on the home page	34
Figure 23 wireframes for the re-build of the VRE online workspace on D4Science, to be implemented in 2023	36
Figure 24 Blue-Cloud ranked third on Revolve for Twitter	37
Figure 25 Example of Twitter post.....	38
Figure 26 Comparison of total engagement for past 12 months with other similar projects	39
Figure 27 Example of a popular LinkedIn post	40
Figure 28 Thumbnail of the Blue-Cloud promotional video	41
Figure 29 Promotional image for the joint policy brief in HRB	51
Figure 30 Visuals from Blue-Cloud workshops	54
Figure 33 Branding for the Blue-Cloud Hackathon.....	55
Figure 34 Infographic with Blue-Cloud hackathon statistics	55
Figure 35 Promotional image and group photo of the Final Conference	56

Glossary

Acronym	Name
CLS	Collecte Localisation Satellites
COVID-19	CoronaVirus Disease 2019
DB	Database
DG	Directorate General
DG CONNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
DG DEFIS	Directorate-General for Defence Industry and Space
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
D5.1	Deliverable 5.1
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ESEB	External Stakeholder & Expert Board
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GRSF	Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M1	Month 1
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisations
VLabs	Virtual Laboratories
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The main goal of the Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholder Engagement activities carried out under Blue-Cloud's WP5 was to raise awareness of, disseminate, and facilitate early adoption of the Blue-Cloud assets, including Key Exploitable Results (KERs), among target stakeholder groups.

The Blue-Cloud "*D5.4 Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholders Engagement Final Report, including events*" reports on the activities and achievements of the project from M19 (April 2021) to M42 (March 2023), building on the "*D5.2 Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholders Engagement Interim Report*", which covered efforts from the project start up to M18 (March 2021).

The main focus of the project during the M19-M42 reported period was to consolidate stakeholder engagement for each target group by disseminating the project's KERs towards promoting uptake and wider exploitation. Aside from the dissemination of technical results, this period was also dedicated to further promoting dialogue and engagement with key stakeholder communities towards the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030, which produced policy recommendations for the further evolution of Blue-Cloud into the decade.

The document is divided in specific sections, listing the key activities and achievements:

Section 1 introduces the current Blue-Cloud community

Section 2 gives an overview of the specific actions undertaken to promote Blue-Cloud KERs and key assets to target stakeholder groups;

Section 3 lists the main communication activities carried out in M19-M41;

Section 4 provides an overview of Blue-Cloud presence at events organised by the project or third-party events, along with other initiatives;

Section 5 is dedicated to the synergies established with different, related initiatives and projects;

Section 6 briefly explains how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted the project and the contingency plans implemented;

Section 7 lists a quick overview of the Key Performance Indicators achieved by M41;

Section 8 summarises and offers an overall conclusion.

1. Overview of the Blue-Cloud community

Through the project lifetime, Blue-Cloud has been able to create a consolidated and engaged community including representatives of the key stakeholder groups identified by the consortium, interested in knowing more about Blue-Cloud services and in learning how to exploit them for their activities. The Blue-Cloud consortium effectively coordinated efforts and activities in support of the dissemination of the different assets towards its community, leading to the achievement in terms of engaged stakeholders as presented in the table below:

Type	Results by M41
Social Media Community	2,400+ Social media followers (1456 Twitter + 782 LinkedIn + 190 YouTube subscribers)
Website Sessions	55,394
Members of ESEB	14
Overall VRE users	1519 from 80+ countries
Synergies Established	33
Roadmap Open Consultation participants	138 (first phase of consultations) + 82 (second phase)
Webinar participants	953 participants over 11 webinars
Newsletter subscribers	830+
Contacts in the Blue-Cloud database	1.830+

Table 1 Blue-Cloud Community

Most of the contacts listed in the Blue-Cloud community database are based in Europe, with particular peaks where consortium partners have stronger networks (e.g., France and Italy). The project was also able to attract interest from other continents, thanks to targeted activities (e.g., a virtual hackathon) and to joint events carried out through its international network, facilitated by partners such as FAO, and the collaboration with initiatives such as the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance, IOC of UNESCO and targeted participation to events with an international scope.

Figure 1 Countries of Blue-Cloud community database members

More than half of the contacts in the Blue-Cloud Community database are from Academia and Research (53%), which is well aligned with the scope of the project, while the second largest sector is represented by government and public authorities with about 12%. Several audiences were involved through different Blue-Cloud activities, such as the Virtual Hackathon, the Roadmap consultations, webinars, and third-party events, reaching out to most of the intended primary stakeholders.

Figure 2 Stakeholder Categories in Blue-Cloud Database

2. Targeted promotion of Blue-Cloud KERs and assets versus target stakeholders

The Key Exploitable Results (KERs) collected and extensively described in “D6.5 Blue-Cloud Services Exploitation and Sustainability Plan” are the core elements promoted and disseminated through the activities carried out in this report. As indicated in “D5.2 Communication, Dissemination & Stakeholders Engagement Interim Report”¹, targeted activities were executed to engage with relevant stakeholders to foster awareness raising and early adoption of the services developed by the project. The table below is an update from the one included in D5.2 linking KERs to target stakeholder groups.

A more detailed overview of user uptake of the different KERs as of the end of the project can be found in “D6.5-Blue-Cloud Services Exploitation and Sustainability Plan” and “D5.3 Blue Cloud Services Uptake Report”.

Key Exploitable Results	PRIMARY STAKEHOLDERS					SECONDARY STAKEHOLDERS	
	Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures	Academia and Researchers	International Organisations	Policy & Funding bodies	Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives	SMEs, Industrial players & Trade Associations	Influencers, hacktivists, NGO’s & general public
KER 1 Virtual Research Environment	X	X	X		X	X	
KER 2 Data Discovery and Access Service	X	X	X		X	X	X
KERs 3-7 Thematic Virtual Labs	X	X	X	X	X	X	
KER 8 Data and Service Catalogue	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Strategic Roadmap to 2030	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 2 Blue-Cloud KERs and assets vs Blue-Cloud Stakeholders

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6337567>

In the following paragraphs we have highlighted some of the target activities organised in this reporting period with the aim to specifically promote and stimulate outreach and uptake of the Blue-Cloud results and assets. They have been complemented with other outreach and communication activities with a broader scope and audience, which are further discussed in chapters 3 and 4.

2.1. Visibility towards the EOSC community

Special effort was dedicated in this second reporting period to ensure visibility for Blue-Cloud towards the EOSC community.

Blue-Cloud value proposition for EOSC

The value proposition of Blue-Cloud in the context of the European Open Science Cloud was clarified in a dedicated webpage², which also links to the 15 Blue-Cloud services that are available via the EOSC Marketplace.

Blue-Cloud value proposition for EOSC

The Blue-Cloud Service platform features a variety of services that can be used for undertaking world-class science via the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** ecosystem, by featuring leading operational marine research infrastructures and e-infrastructures. Blue-Cloud supports the view of EOSC and expects EOSC to provide:

- A pilot **thematic EOSC as a role model** for the development of other thematic clouds. The cyber-platform of Blue-Cloud provides FAIR access to multidisciplinary data, analytical tools and computing and storage facilities that support research.
- **Blue-Cloud Services** showcased through five Demonstrators for ocean, seas and freshwater bodies for ecosystems research, conservation, forecasting and innovation in the Blue Economy, and making innovative use of seamless access to multidisciplinary data, algorithms, and computing resources - accelerating cross-discipline science.
- A **methodology for researchers interacting with e-infrastructure developers** to establish a cyber platform with tools and services, which support multiple scientific challenges and are fit-for-purpose, while built upon generic core principles and services.
- A **mechanism to easily access and discover blue data**. Blue-Cloud partners manage important volumes of blue data (e.g., SeaDataNet, EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, etc.) and links have been established with major European research infrastructures and observing networks to increase the data volume.
- APIs to access blue services that will **complement EOSC base services** providing blue thematic functionalities.
- Dynamic examples of how a framework like Blue-Cloud can **address one or several of the policy challenges** defined in the Bioeconomy Strategy, the Circular Economy Strategy, the Blue Growth Strategy, the Common Fisheries Policy, the Maritime

² <https://blue-cloud.org/services/blue-cloud-contribution-european-open-science-cloud-eosc>

Spatial Planning Directive, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the International Ocean Governance Communication and the UN SDGs.

- **A global Blue Economy community** close to the EOSC vision, including the marine and maritime industry.
- The opportunity of **bringing EOSC in the Blue Economy long-term vision** via the policy-oriented [Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030](#) which seeks a series of EU Calls for further development and uptake of the Blue Cloud by multiple VRE applications and connecting additional marine data services and research infrastructures.

The Blue-Cloud Open platform is a great example of implementation of the three main components of the EOSC Federation - EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and the Federation of Data & Data Services - into a unique Open Science platform accessible and usable by other research communities. Blue-Cloud is a front runner of Data federation in practice, given its success in bringing together 9 data providers covering 10M datasets from the marine domain and making them available via the DD&AS and the VRE to users, allowing interdisciplinary interactions between disciplines, thus demonstrating the value of bringing together a variety of providers and users within EOSC.

Delivering for EOSC: Blue-Cloud featured in the “Key Exploitable Results of the Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects Report”

Over the course of 2022 the EOSC Association produced a brochure-style document describing the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects still active as of the spring of 2022. The information was provided by the projects through a survey questionnaire that was developed in collaboration between the EOSC Association and the Research Data Alliance Association (RDA). The survey collected responses from 22 projects, which reported a total of 119 KERs, covering mainly technical and policy harmonisation efforts, virtual research environments, discovery/access platforms, training resources, knowledge centres and validation tools. The KERs identified in this survey of Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects show strong correlations to the EOSC Advisory Groups (AG) topics, with maximum relevance for “Technical challenges in EOSC” and “Implementation of EOSC”; high relevance for “Metadata and data quality”; and satisfactory relevance for the AG topics “Research careers and curricula” and “Sustaining the EOSC”.

Blue-Cloud contributed to this effort and completed the survey, and a sample of its KERs were featured in the report which was distributed and promoted at several key events by the EOSC Association, starting from the EOSC Symposium held in September 2022 in Prague.

The report was released as full report³ as well as a short summary report⁴.

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7401539>

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7404164>

Figure 3 Delivering for EOSC: Key Exploitable Results of the Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects (Summary report), Blue-Cloud Key Exploitable Results

Blue-Cloud Open Science platform as a model for a sustainable Data federation in EOSC: workshop at the EOSC Symposium 2022

The Blue-Cloud model, with its 15 services and million datasets openly available, was discussed during a dedicated session organised on the 17th of November 2022 at the EOSC Symposium, the main annual event of the European Open Science community that took place in Prague, Czech Republic.

What should a data federation look like? What are the financial models laying behind the marine data that researchers access and use for their applications and experiments? What recommendations can we give to funders as well as to the private sector towards sustainability of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data in the long run?

These aspects and more were at the heart of the session hosted by Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Blue-Cloud Coordinator, on Thursday 17th and moderated by Jessica Klemeier, EMBL and member of the EOSC Sustainability Task Force⁵. Anton Ellenbroek, FAO of the UN, Knowledge and Information Management Team of the Fisheries and Aquaculture Division, Karl Presser, Managing Partner at Premotec GmbH and FNS-Cloud H2020 representative and Alessandro Rizzo, IRD and FAIR-EASE⁶ project representative, joined the session and helped contextualising the Blue-Cloud best practice within a European and even international framework.

The panel discussion leveraged on the considerations included in the Progress report “Towards Funding Model Scenarios for Financial Sustainability of EOSC”⁷ released by the EOSC

⁵ <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/financial-sustainability>

⁶ <https://fairease.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-11/financial-sustainability-tf-progress-report-nov-2022.pdf>

Task Force on Financial Sustainability, part of the EOSC Advisory Group “Sustaining EOSC”, that was released the following month of October 2022. Blue-Cloud was included among four use cases, chosen according to the expertise available within the Task Force, where federation of research data had already been successfully accomplished. Silvana Muscella, Trust-IT CEO and Blue-Cloud Project Management Office is among the authors of the report.

Figure 4 Panel session during the workshop organised by Blue-Cloud at the EOSC Symposium 2022

A dedicated event page is available online⁸, while a post event article was published a few days after the event⁹ and further disseminated.

2.2. Visibility towards the Digital Ocean Twinning Community

On 20-21 April 2022 the first Digital Ocean Forum took place in Paris, the first milestone of the very ambitious project initiated by Mercator Ocean International, the European Commission and the French Ministry of the Sea to design a virtual ocean running factory from science to private. 70 experts representing historic and new actors in the marine panorama

⁸ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/open-science-platform-data-federation-eosc-symposium-2022>

⁹ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/blue-cloud-open-science-platform-model-sustainable-data-federation-eosc-workshop-eosc-symposium>

gathered physically together to provide their input on accessing ocean data, ocean modelling, ocean intelligence, digital framework and international collaboration.

Sara Pittonet Gaiairin, Project Coordinator, and Dick Schaap, Technical Coordinator, joined the Digital Ocean Forum. On the 20th of March Sara Pittonet joined the Working Group dedicated to Ocean Intelligence, coordinated by Akrivi Kiousi (INTRASOFT) and Arne Berre (SINTEF) and chaired by DG MARE Zoi Konstantinou, bringing to the discussion the feedback and lessons learned from the creation of Blue-Cloud valuable ground-base services at the e-Infrastructure level (such as the Data Discovery and Access Service to find and retrieve datasets from 9 marine federated data providers, or the cloud computing and analytics facilities available in the Blue-Cloud Gateway) as well as the 12 thematic services released as part of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs, real-life research-based scenarios for biodiversity, genomics, environment, fisheries and aquaculture. Dick Schaap joined the WG1 on accessing Ocean Data and new sensors, while Blue-Cloud partners Jan-Bart Calewaert and Kate Larkin from Seascope Belgium and EMODnet Secretariat, also joined the event.

The forum was followed by a Policy Forum on the 21st of March, where the role of Blue-Cloud within this infrastructure was clarified by Pierre Bahurel, Director General Mercator Ocean International.

Figure 5 Pierre Bahurel, Director General Mercator Ocean International, introducing the DTO Mission to mobilise strategic actors at the Digital Ocean Forum

Blue-Cloud is seen as one of the founding research components, offering e-infrastructure services (computing, storage, analytical, SSO, AAI and generic services to be orchestrated with a large variety of data resources), federated data (10M+ datasets and products from leading European marine data management infrastructures (COPERNICUS C3S, COPERNICUS CMEMS, ELIXIR-ENA, EMODnet, Euro-Argo, Argo GDAC, EuroBioImaging, EurOBIS, ICOS-Marine and SeaDataNet), and research intensive virtual labs. Blue-Cloud also offers an entry level to EOSC, where services and products can be exploited and used in the future EU Digital Twin Ocean

(DTO) and where an active community of research stakeholder is piloting Open Access services for cross-disciplinary purposes.

The outcomes of the event are collected in an **article** published and distributed afterwards¹⁰.

Further contacts with the DTO Community allowed Blue-Cloud to establish synergies with the **ILIAD** project¹¹, funded to establish an interoperable, data-intensive, and cost-effective Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) as reported in *D6.6*, and the EDITO projects led by Mercator Ocean, to be further continued within the remit of the Blue-Cloud2026 initiative.

2.3. Visibility towards the UN and Atlantic communities

Over the course of the project, we have experienced a gradual growth in the awareness that Blue-Cloud and key international initiatives, such as the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE) of the IOC UNESCO could learn and benefit from each other.

An interview with Peter Pissierssens¹² – Head, IOC Project Office for IODE and IOC CD Coordinator at UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission, as well as member of the Blue-Cloud External Stakeholders Expert Board – in January 2022 highlighted the upcoming increased collaboration, as Blue-Cloud would support IOC and IODE to develop the next layers, going from ocean data collection, management, and the development of products, in order to become more relevant to society and provide services for policymakers and other ocean stakeholders.

On the other hand, as also shown in the evolution of the community in Section 1, IODE as a global network helped widen the EU-based initial scope of Blue-Cloud, while the latter provided concrete examples of long-standing expertise through the data infrastructures involved (such as EMODnet and SeaDataNet), operating in the field over twenty years.

¹⁰ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/digital-twin-ocean-2027-impressions-digital-ocean-forum>

¹¹ <https://www.ocean-twin.eu/iliad-project-overview>

¹² <https://youtu.be/grk-aFKqcvM>

Figure 6 A screenshot from the interview with Peter Pissierssens

In addition, as part of the synergies programme, Blue-Cloud has strengthened its cooperation with the All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation (AANChOR) project. Blue-Cloud and AANChOR have established a strong synergy focused on communication and dissemination activities. The cooperation spanned from the organisation of joint events and promotional activities on the projects’ main channels.

In total, the projects have collaborated on five joint events that helped Blue-Cloud present its overarching goals to an international community. The full list of co-organised events by Blue-Cloud and AANChOR can be found in the Table below:

Event title	Date	Event scope
Improving the knowledge of our oceans and seas and bringing them closer to citizens	5 February 2020	Contribute to the implementation of the Galway and the Belém Statements by better understanding the international data/e-infrastructure landscape and the needed federation efforts to accelerate the establishment of a global “Blue-Cloud” able to effectively and efficiently bring data at the service of society.
All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum 2020	6 – 7 February 2020	Forum to showcase the results of cooperation and their impact on the citizens living on the shores of the Atlantic.
Towards an All-Atlantic Data Space	3 June 2021	Co-organisation of a joint workshop as a side event at the All-Atlantic 2021. The workshop provided an arena to share the current capability of marine data collection, sharing and services across the Atlantic Ocean, and to debate about EU and international initiatives working to harmonise and facilitate data sharing across the Atlantic, and offered insight into available facilities, tools, training, and the latest open science ‘blue cloud’ technologies to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

Event title	Date	Event scope
Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond	14 December 2021	Presentation of the joint policy brief developed in the framework of the EC-funded Horizon Results Booster.
South African Webinar & Virtual Workshop	24 May 2022	Participation into the scientific forum to support the dialogue towards sustainable perspectives, priorities and activities connected to the All-Atlantic Declaration.

Table 3 Blue-Cloud and AANChOR co-organised events

Some of the projects involved also co-wrote a joint policy brief in the context of the EC-funded Horizon Results Booster, listing recommendations for sustainable ocean observation and management and was developed. More details on this in section 3.9.

2.4. Promotion of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS)

Stakeholders: Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures, Academia and Researchers, International Organisations, Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives, Influencers, hacktivists, NGO’s & general public

Over the course of the second reporting period, the Data Discovery and Access Service moved from the first public presentations of the beta release in September 2021 to a full release in September 2022, when a specific communication campaign was launched to promote the Data Discovery and Access Service. A press release promoting the Data Discovery and Access Service was published in November 2021¹³.

2.4.1. Video interviews

In September 2022 an interview with Dick Schaap, MARIS, Blue-Cloud Technical Coordinator dedicated to the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service was launched and promoted on the Blue-Cloud website and on social media channels as well as via the newsletter. In that occasion the main DD&AS page on the website¹⁴ was also updated.

In addition, the series of interviews with representatives of the data infrastructures launched in the first reporting period also saw new ones, providing a clearer idea of the types of data federated in Blue-Cloud and their relevance to practical use cases in the Virtual Labs.

Figure 7 The interview with Dick Schaap on the DD&AS

¹³ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/setting-sail-blue-cloud-data-discovery-access-service>

¹⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/services/blue-cloud-data-discovery-and-access-service>

These are the interviews with data infrastructure representatives that were published over the course of Blue-Cloud:

- 30 December 2020 – Jean Olivier Irisson (EcoTaxa) <https://blue-cloud.org/news/blue-cloud-data-infrastructures-interview-jean-olivier-irisson-ecotaxa>
- 9 March 2021 – Guy Cochrane (European Nucleotide Archive) <https://blue-cloud.org/news/ena-bringing-quality-nucleotide-sequencing-information-blue-cloud-interview-guy-cochrane>
- 28 April 2021 – Thierry Carval (Euro-Argo) <https://www.blue-cloud.org/news/euro-argo-contributing-excellent-situ-ocean-observing-data-blue-cloud-interview-thierry-carval>
- 27 June 2022 – Kate Larkin (EMODnet) <https://youtu.be/z6b3LVtJNQ4>
- 12 July 2022 – Lennert Schepers and Patricia Cabrera (VLIZ – EurOBIS) https://youtu.be/GGbWOpC_NM

Figure 8 Shots from the interviews with data infrastructures representatives

2.4.2. EOSC in practice story

As part of its awareness raising activities, the EOSC Future project, the EU-funded H2020 project that is implementing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), is preparing and disseminating a series of EOSC in practice stories¹⁵ to showcase concrete examples of Open Science practices implementing EOSC guidelines and principles and using resources available in the EOSC Marketplace.

The key distinctive features of these easy-to-read summaries are the following:

¹⁵ The full list of EOSC in practice stories is available [here](#)

- They should describe a resource that is already integrated or soon-to-be/planned to be available on the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace.
- The importance/role of EOSC is explained.
- The impact on society and various stakeholder categories is described.
- Cross-disciplinary elements are highlighted.
- Sustainability plans or future funding models are identified or at least in discussion.

In February 2022 a story titled “Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research” dedicated to the Data Discovery and Access Service was produced and distributed via the EOSC portal channels. The story is also available on Zenodo here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646200>

Figure 9 EOSC In practice story “Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research”

2.4.3. Posters and presentations

The Beta Release of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service was first presented and demonstrated by Peter Thijsse (MARIS) at the Open Science FAIR 2021¹⁶.

¹⁶ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-open-science-fair-2021>

Figure 10 Peter Thijsse presenting the DD&AS at OSFAIR 2021

A video tutorial was produced in January 2022 to support and guide participants of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, and made available via the Blue-Cloud YouTube channel¹⁷ for wider dissemination.

The full release was then presented in September 2022 by Dick Schaap (MARIS) at the EGI Conference 2022¹⁸, with a general poster about Blue-Cloud, featuring the DD&AS link on top as a core service, and also with a presentation focusing on the success on data federation in Blue-Cloud, exploited via the DD&AS.

Figure 11 Poster and slides presented at EGI 2022

¹⁷ <https://youtu.be/s00j1-UgKE>

¹⁸ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-egi-conference-2022>

2.5. Target promotion of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

Stakeholders: Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures, Academia and Researchers, International Organisations, Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives, Influencers, hacktivists, NGO’s & general public

2.5.3. User survey with VRE users

In order to collect some more feedback from early adopters of the Blue-Cloud services, a short user survey was carried out in the summer of 2022. The idea was to ask some easy questions to people that had already tested Blue-Cloud at least once, so as to get a clearer idea of their background and needs. In order to make the campaign even more attractive, one respondent would have been randomly chosen by the Blue-Cloud Steering Board to take part as a member of the audience to the Blue-Cloud Final Conference in Brussels.

After a campaign mainly targeting existing users via direct email, we received 45 responses through August and early September. A vast majority of polled users looked for Blue-Cloud services in order to discover and download datasets, followed by almost half of respondents who were interested in demonstrators’ tools in the Virtual Labs, and then to collaborate with other colleagues.

Figure 12 Statistics on the purpose of Blue-Cloud usage in the user survey

In terms of functionalities, according to users the most useful ones were the Data Discovery and Access Service, the domain-specific Virtual Labs, followed by JupyterHub notebook and storage in the workspace.

Figure 13 Statistics on the functionalities thought as most useful in the user survey

The free participation in the Blue-Cloud Final Conference was awarded to Marco Fianchini, Doctorate student at the Oceanography Section of OGS in Italy, who shared the following comment about his experience.

“Blue-Cloud services helped me scale up my analysis in a friendly environment. Virtual Research Environments are helpful examples of research workflows and best practices and services such as DataMiner are an amazing set of readily available tools to learn by doing.

I had the pleasure to attend the Blue-Cloud Final Conference in Brussels as a guest. It was an amazing moment, in a prestigious location, to meet in person the community of researchers and developers behind this project. It is amazing how diverse but connected was the community.”

2.5.4. Tutorial on the usage of the VRE

One of the main technical components of the Blue-Cloud technical framework is the Virtual Research Environment (VRE), that includes services that facilitate collaboration between users, services supporting the execution of analytical tasks embedded in a distributed computing infrastructure.

In order to guide external users on the usage and functioning of the Blue-Cloud VRE, an online tutorial was organised on 7 October 2022 led by Massimiliano Assante, IT Operations Manager at D4Science Infrastructure. The training was joined live by representatives of the projects JERICO, Jonas, EuroSea and

Training Session on the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environments

Blue-Cloud
193 subscribers

47 views 4 months ago Blue-Cloud tutorials

The Blue-Cloud project is federating distributed marine #data resources, computing platforms, and analytical services to better understand and manage the many aspects of #ocean sustainability. In order to do so, a "Blue-Cloud technical framework" has been set-up, where leading mar Show more

DOORS, following their request of attending a live tutorial to better understand the VRE offer.

The recording of the session was published on Blue-Cloud Youtube¹⁹ channel and included in the Support Centre accessible from the Blue-Cloud website.

The Virtual Research Environment was also presented by Pasquale Pagano at the Open Science FAIR 2021²⁰, and a dedicated tutorial for the Blue-Cloud Hackathon participants was published in January 2022 and made available via YouTube²¹.

2.5.5. EOSC in practice story

A second EOSC in practice story is being prepared by the EOSC Future team together with Pasquale Pagano, Senior Researcher at CNR and D4Science Technical Director, about the Blue-Cloud VRE as common workspace provided to researchers in the marine world to analyse, process, share data and co-develop research products. Currently under review at the time of writing, it will be released over the course of Spring 2023.

2.6. Promotion of the Thematic Virtual Labs

Stakeholders: Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures, Academia and Researchers, Policy & Funding bodies, International Organisations, Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives.

The multi-disciplinary **Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs**²², configured with specific analytical workflows and serving as real-life Demonstrators, can be adopted and adapted for other inputs and analyses. These Blue-Cloud V Labs showcase (reproducible) analytical methods and workflows that have been developed to support marine researchers across different thematic areas, and which can trigger new, community-driven applications to support wider policy and societal goals. A comprehensive package of webinars and promotional activities was launched to give outreach to Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs, as described in this section.

2.6.1. Blue-Cloud VLab Webinars

The Blue-Cloud webinars²³ demonstrated the added value that the Blue-Cloud framework and demonstrators can bring to communities dealing with grand societal challenges. The webinars also played a key role in educating how these communities could use the Blue-Cloud services and data.

A total of 11 webinars were organised which counted 953 attendees. The webinars were opened with a general one, with an overview of all Blue-Cloud demonstrators. This episode was followed by 2 series of webinars, with 5 episodes each. The first series, from 2020 and early 2021, was focused on introductions and beta-version demonstrations of the 5 V Labs. The second series of webinars, from 2021 and early 2022, was dedicated to presenting the public V Labs.

As seen in the table below (Table 12), the average number of participants registered was 87, with an average participation of 54 unique viewers. These results surpass the KPI of having at least 30 participants on average per webinar. On average, the webinars had a 59% rate of effective participants

¹⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qZzUHLLeQamU&list=PLXh8gTuBcNt74UkyrP279iaT22zcbnwn>

²⁰ <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-open-science-fair-2021>

²¹ <https://youtu.be/qCa8zfyouF8>

²² <https://blue-cloud.org/vlabs>

²³ <https://blue-cloud.org/blue-cloud-webinar>

of the total registered. The recordings of the webinars, accessible after the webinar through both the Blue-Cloud website and YouTube channel, were watched 156,5 times on average.

Webinar	Registrants	Unique viewers	% of registrants participating	YouTube views	Unique view + YouTube views
19-06-2020 Blue-Cloud demonstrators	121	102	84,3%	162	203
25-09-2020 Aquaculture Monitor	135	88,0	65,2%	530	158
14-10-2020 Fish, a matter of scales	94	62,0	66,0%	204	139
04-12-2020 Marine Environmental Indicators	98	61,0	62,2%	194	143
12-02-2021 Zoo & Phytoplankton EOY Products	174	102	58,6%	263	102
23-04-2021 Plankton Genomics	108	70	64,8%	90	160
24-03-2022 Test the Virtual Labs - Zoo & Phytoplankton EOY Products	75	30	40%	74	104
13-05-2022 Test the Virtual Labs - Plankton Genomics	41	26	63,4%	44	70
25-05-2022 Test the Virtual Labs - Marine Environmental Indicators	40	19	47,5%	53	72
20-06-2022 Test the Virtual Labs - Aquaculture Monitor	47	21	44,7%	60	81
12-10-2022 Fisheries Atlas - a flexible Spatial Data Infrastructure at the FAO	20	11	55%	45	56
AVERAGE	86,6	53,8	59,25%	156,27	117,1

Table 4 Statistics from Blue-Cloud webinars

The Blue-Cloud team believes the decrease of participants is due to the trend of “webinar fatigue”, a feeling that viewers experience after attending numerous video meetings and webinars. It usually refers to a malaise at the thought of attending more online events. This was a common issue after the gradual reopening following the COVID-19 pandemic, where the organisation of online events was a solution to overcome travel restrictions. It is clear that from March 2022, when the travel restrictions started to smooth and the organisation of physical events was becoming slowly part of our daily routine, the number of online participants decreased, while opportunities for face-to-face events increased.

2.6.2. VLab Article series

Five articles were prepared over the course of this second reporting period in collaboration with the leaders of the Virtual Labs. They are all available on the Blue-Cloud website as well as on Blue-Cloud Community on Zenodo. A glossy version was also produced for easier dissemination.

Date	Title	Views	Downloads	Link
17.05.2021	Applying machine learning methods to ocean patterns and ocean regimes indicators Authors: Marketakis, Yannis; Ellenbroek, Anton; Gentile, Aureliano; Drago, Federico	111	81	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5896651
15.07.2021	Developing zoo & phytoplankton EOV products in Blue-Cloud Authors: Cabrera, Patricia; Pint, Steven; Schepers, Lennert; Everaert, Gert; Renosh, Pannimpullath Remanan; Barth, Alexander; Drago, Federico	130	107	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5896680
29.09.2021	Monitoring aquaculture activities through high-resolution satellite images Authors: Augot, Jérémy; Fatras, Christophe; Lavergne, Emeric; Longépé, Nicolas; Valdaine, R.; Ellenbroek, Anton; Drago, Federico	103	61	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5902386
17.11.2021	Federating knowledge on stocks and fisheries in Blue-Cloud with the GRSF Authors: Marketakis, Yannis; Ellenbroek, Anton; Gentile, Aureliano; Drago, Federico	50	34	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5902487
22.02.2022	Exploring and mapping plankton genomics data with Blue-Cloud Authors: Debeljak, Pavla; Schickele, Alexandre; Ayata, Sakina-Dorothee; Bittner, Lucie; Irisson, Jean-Olivier; Drago, Federico	124	57	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6224852

Table 5 The five articles dedicated to the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs

Figure 14 Promotional visual for the five articles on Zenodo

2.6.3. Blue-Cloud use case on WEKEO

Blue-Cloud was recently [featured on the official WEKEO website](#) as a successful example of “Collaborative Open Science platform for marine research”, particularly highlighting the innovation of the Data Discovery & Access Service, enabling access to more than 10 million datasets from Copernicus, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, Euro-Argo, ENA, EcoTaxa, SOCAT, ICOS, EurOBIS, via a single MarineID.

The Blue-Cloud use case highlights how WEKEO also helped enhance the quality of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment and Virtual Labs in different ways (such as: Harmonised online access to the full WEKEO product catalogue; Updates of products notified and promptly available for online access; Integrated cost-effective data access and processing system ; Application scalability sustained by the WEKEO evolution) and how specific WEKEO products are exploited in the Marine Environmental Indicators Virtual Lab, which provides an analytics service to support monitoring and management activities for the marine environment on a regional scale, starting from the Mediterranean Sea.

A piece of news was written in September 2022²⁴ and distributed across both Blue-Cloud and WEKEO channels.

2.6.4. Interviews

Five interviews explaining the challenges addressed and potential benefits of the Virtual Labs were recorded at the project kick-off and made available between January and February 2020.

- Lennert Schepers and Lennert Tyberghein (VLIZ) – Zoo & Phytoplankton EOVS Products
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9WwvKT1Gid0>

²⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/marine-environment-copernicus-wekeo-dias>

- Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI), Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI), Jean-Olivier Irisson (Sorbonne Université) – Plankton Genomics
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GUiE281pawY>
- Massimiliano Drudi (CMCC) – Marine Environmental Indicators
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z2czFSAktKU>
- Anton Ellenbroek (FAO) - Fish, a matter of scales
 - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LxzdYtWZ_1g
- Anton Ellenbroek (FAO) – Aquaculture Monitor
 - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f2-5Oq7-VzI>

2.6.5. VLab factsheets

A **series of at-a-glance factsheets presenting the Virtual Labs** was produced for the Blue-Cloud Final Conference, and then collected in a booklet²⁵ distributed at the Blue-Cloud 2026 Kick-off meeting in February 2023, including descriptions of the benefits, target users, main societal and scientific impacts, along with key facts about their usage and testimonials from users.

In these factsheets, Blue-Cloud experts from VLIZ, Sorbonne University, CMCC, FAO explained what researchers can do in these thematic V Labs, also highlighting the societal challenges they will contribute to tackling. Five factsheets are available online both in the project website and in the Blue-Cloud community on Zenodo:

- [Zoo & Phytoplankton EOY Products](#)
- [Plankton Genomics](#)
- [Marine Environmental Indicators](#)
- [Fish, a matter of scales](#)
- [Aquaculture Monitor](#)

In addition to these, we have also produced factsheets for the three top teams awarded at the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, providing real-life examples of applications for Blue-Cloud assets in the blue economy.

- [Sea Clearly](#) - A tool to assess ocean plastic impacts on and by aquaculture farms
- [PerfeCt](#) - Performance of Aquaculture under Climate change
- [Wildlife Tracker for Oceans](#) - MPA assessment with real-time wildlife tracking & ocean monitoring data

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663960>

Figure 15 Cover and one factsheet from the collection

2.7. Promotion of the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap 2030

Stakeholders: Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures, Academia and Researchers, Policy & Funding bodies, International Organisations, Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives, Influencers, hacktivists, NGO's & general public

The Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030²⁶ is a strategic policy document guiding the future development of Blue-Cloud's efforts as a leading component of EOOSC for the marine community. With some iterations during the project lifetime, its final version was presented at the Blue-Cloud Final Conference that took place in Brussels on the 8th December 2022.

The drafting of the Roadmap required close and regular dialogue with key stakeholder communities, including blue data and e-infrastructures, marine scientists & researchers, international organisations, policy and funding bodies from different sectors, as well as with industry.

Initiated and steered by the Blue-Cloud Consortium with the support of its External Stakeholders Expert Board and of an interdisciplinary, cross-sectoral Expert Foresight Group, the roadmap has been co-designed with the wider marine and ICT community via extensive stakeholder consultations. A variety of tools to harness stakeholder input and foresight contributions were put in place, including workshops, online surveys, targeted interviews, and open feedback sessions.

2.7.1. Support to the Roadmap open consultation

The first round of consultations for the Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap, led by Seascope Belgium with the support of Trust-IT and MARIS, was described in D5.2²⁷. During this first phase an online survey was run with the wider community in October 2020, which collected over 130 contributions.

²⁶ <https://blue-cloud.org/services/blue-cloud-strategic-roadmap-2030>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6337567>

The second phase of stakeholder dialogue ran between June 2021 and March 2022. It was led by Seascope Belgium, Trust-IT Services and MARIS, and encompassed a **public consultation** and **targeted interviews with key stakeholders** from research institutes and infrastructures, European and global Ocean observing and data management initiatives, Blue Economy and policy representatives, EOSC related initiatives and other groups, as well as bringing in feedback from participants engaged in the [Blue-Cloud Hackathon](#).

Differently from the broader scope of the first open consultation in 2020, which aimed at gathering as many contributions as possible from the wider marine & maritime community in Europe and internationally, the second round went a bit more in depth on the topics covered by the Roadmap.

WP5 provided support for the second round of consultations, launched in **June 2021** with a public campaign²⁸ on the website, social media, newsletters, and through direct engagement with stakeholders.

Figure 16 Promotional image for the Roadmap Public Consultation (left) and promotion on social media (right)

²⁸ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/help-shape-future-blue-cloud-take-survey>

A total of **82 survey responses** were obtained through the webform, complemented with targeted interviews. This phase of the Roadmap evolution was also described in a blog post and a short video with Julia Vera (Seascope Belgium) from WP6²⁹ in May 2022.

Figure 17 Sample of the outcomes of the Roadmap survey run in the second open consultation phase

These inputs were then exploited to further polish the roadmap (D6.4) and presented publicly at the Blue-Cloud Final Conference in December 2022. A condensed summary was also produced for this occasion³⁰, published on Zenodo and distributed to the 100 participants of the Final Event, featuring the key elements and easy-to-read infographics.

Figure 18 Cover of Roadmap Executive Summary

2.7.2. Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshops

A total of four Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshops were organised, from which three were organised in close cooperation with Blue-Cloud ESEB members, and the fourth one was organised as a Policy

²⁹ <https://blue-cloud.org/news/developing-blue-cloud-strategic-roadmap-2030-together>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377985>

Dialogue, where participation was possible due to invitation only (see table 10). Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, all events were organised online.

Date	Event title	Goal
01.07.2020	Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshop with ESEB	Discuss initial steps towards building the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030.
20.11.2020	Blue-Cloud Policy Dialogue: Co-creating the Roadmap to 2030	Consult different Directorate-Generals of the European Commission on their vision and expectations for Blue-Cloud, in order to build their input into early discussions on the first draft of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030.
02.12.2020	Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshop with ESEB	Exchange reflections on the preliminary results of early stakeholder dialogue with the Blue-Cloud community, as well as on the initial blueprint for the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030, built on results from consultation.
19.05.2021	Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshop with ESEB	Discuss the Roadmap towards its release for public consultation, as well as collect new inputs/suggestions to be included. Another goal was to discuss the communication & outreach strategy of the public consultation, to maximise broad participation.

Table 6 Roadmap and policy workshops with ESEB

Figure 19 Blue-Cloud Policy Dialogue: Co-creating the Roadmap to 2030” branding

The organisation of these workshops in close cooperation with interdisciplinary ESEB, along with the policy dialogue where inputs were collected from Policy Makers, were relevant to design a roadmap focused on the wider marine and ICT community, combined with stakeholder consultations, online surveys and interviews done during the project timeframe.

3. Outreach and dissemination activities M19-M42

WP5 provided updates and information to target groups and the wider community about project activities and results, via a variety of tools such as news, events, webinars, social media channels, newsletters, posters, documents, videos, and more.

3.1. Blue-Cloud public Website

The Blue-Cloud website www.blue-cloud.org was launched on 23 December 2019, acting as the central digital hub for communication and engagement. It was revamped in February 2022, following the evolution of the project, giving more space to the services and Virtual Labs³¹.

Since the updates described in D5.2, a complete revamp of the homepage layout was introduced, by adding a video background for the hero section on top and changing the elements in the homepage structure. At the first scroll, users could now find direct links to the Data Discovery & Access Service, the test environment of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Lab, and the Blue-Cloud Catalogue. At the second scroll, links to the five Virtual Labs.

Figure 20 Blue-Cloud website homepage

Figure 21 Blue-Cloud website homepage first scroll with services

³¹ <https://twitter.com/BlueCloudEU/status/1495727207439810565?s=20>

Figure 22 Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs on the home page

Between M19 (April 2021) and M41 (February 2023), has seen an evolution in terms of visits, which were regularly over the internal KPI of 800+ monthly sessions through most of the project lifetime. Website traffic in general followed the main project activities such as webinars, workshops, the hackathon, then in particular one issue has started affecting website traffic in the second half of 2022.

KPI	M36/42	February 2023 M41
Users	13,200	44,576
Sessions	28,800	55,394
Monthly sessions	800	1,457.7

Table 7 Website KPIs

In particular, a stricter approach to website analytics was adopted across the board since June 2022, clearly allowing users to choose if they wanted to accept analytics cookies or not, had a major influence on existing traffic going “underground” and undetected by analytics.

It is possible to infer that about 20% of visitors do not accept the tracking, while a few others (about 4%) customise their preferences, and therefore we can only assume what they do on the website after that.

Nevertheless, visits have started growing again – also with the new settings – after the summer, towards the Final Conference and the beginning of Blue-Cloud 2026 in early 2023.

It should be noted that the Virtual Research Environment and the Data Discovery and Access Service do not share the same analytics as the website, as they are separate environments.

The three most popular pages of the Blue-Cloud website in terms of visits - aside from the home page - were the following:

- Page on the Blue-Cloud Final Conference³² - 1221 views
- About Blue-Cloud³³ - 755 views
- Zoo and Phytoplankton EOV Products³⁴ - 586 views

3.1.1. Website evolution

During the course of the project, the website public interface and the VRE online workspace on D4Science were both assessed by project partners and third-party users. An internal feedback assessment was also run with some of the VLab representatives to check how to improve usability of the VRE workspace as well as the public website.

As an outcome of this assessment, a series of wireframes and user journeys were prepared, as guidelines to be followed for the re-build of both portals.

³² <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-final-conference-open-science-eu-green-deal>

³³ A first overview of the results can be found here: <https://www.blue-cloud.org/news/blue-cloud-roadmap-2030-unwrapping-first-consultation-results>

³⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/vlabs/zoo-and-phytoplankton-eov-products>

About Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment
 Welcome to Blue-Cloud one-stop shop where scientists can contribute, find, try, and use Blue-Cloud methods as integrated in the infrastructure by scientists across multiple disciplines. Using the VRE user interface scientists can, with the support of an on-line file-sharing workspace, execute methods on high-performance backends and implement scientific workflows satisfying their needs.

VRE Computing services and analytics facilities

Blue-Cloud Labs

Data Discovery & Access

Cloud resources offered by

About D4Science

Welcome to Blue-Cloud one-stop shop where scientists can contribute, find, try, and use Blue-Cloud methods as integrated in the infrastructure by scientists across multiple disciplines. Using the VRE user interface scientists can, with the support of an on-line file-sharing workspace, execute methods on high-performance backends and implement scientific workflows satisfying their needs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT EU FUNDING

VRE Computing services

Blue-Cloud Project Labs

Blue-Cloud Demonstrators

VLabs for other communities

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT EU FUNDING

Figure 23 wireframes for the re-build of the VRE online workspace on D4Science, to be implemented in 2023

3.2.Social media

The social media activity of Blue-Cloud focused on its **Twitter**, **LinkedIn** and **YouTube** channels, providing an instant form of communication with community members and potentially interested people or organisations out of the community. Through frequent activity and interaction, the outreach team ensured continual visibility of the project’s efforts such as technical updates, events, webinars, new materials, consultations. Social media channels especially supported community building by providing a path from seeing the messages to potentially converting as an engaged stakeholder.

All envisioned KPIs were met apart from the impressions on LinkedIn, where we still managed to outgrow the intended number in terms of followers, successfully laying the foundation for the follow-up project Blue-Cloud 2026 to build on.

Channel	KPI by M36	February 2023 M41
Twitter	1,000 followers	1,456 followers
	700,000 impressions	1,079,200 impressions
	700 tweets	1,000+ tweets
LinkedIn	600 followers	782 followers
	100,000 impressions	74,216 impressions
YouTube	6 videos	36 videos (excluding webinars and workshops)
	500 views per video across channels	35,667 total views on YouTube channel

Table 8 Social Media KPIs

3.2.1. Twitter

As of M41 (February 2023), the Twitter community has grown to more than 1400 followers, becoming the third largest tracked by the portal Revolve, as shown in the image below³⁵.

Figure 24 Blue-Cloud ranked third on Revolve for Twitter

@BlueCloudEU has reached **1456 followers** (an **84.7% increase** since D5.2 in March 2021), consolidating its role as one of the most visible accounts at the crossroads between the marine research, Open Science, and blue economy communities, collecting mentions and follows from relevant profiles across the board. Examples of these can be found in the table below.

³⁵ <https://revolve.media/rankings/social-media/twitter/>

Community	Profiles (followers)
Marine research	@UFollowtheOcean (5.8k), @Havforskningen (6.6k), @GalwayAquarium (4k), @AllAtlanticO (3300+), @Euromarine_tw (3300+), @CommOceanConf (1900+), @LeibnizZMT (1400+)
EOSC and Open Science	@openscience (72.4k), @EuCitSci (5.8k), @FutureTechEU (8.6k), @eoscassociation (1500+), @EoscPortal (3000+), @EOSCFuture (1200+), @OpenScienceFAIR (1800+)
Blue Economy	@easaqua (3.8k) @OceanDecadeECOP (2900+), @EATIP_eu (1800+), @OceanCouncil (1500+), @SEAentia (1300+)
Policy	@IPBES (118k), @ciencia_pt (22.4k), @UN_FAO_GFCM (9k), @EULawDataPubs (8k), @Searica_ITG (2100+), @IODEocean (1000+)

Table 9 Examples of popular followers on Twitter

Figure 25 Example of Twitter post

The Twitter account is one of the key legacy elements for communications handed over to the follow-up Blue-Cloud 2026 project, which has started co-managing the channel in January 2023.

3.2.2. LinkedIn

Following on the LinkedIn account Blue-Cloud Org³⁶ saw a **97% increase** from 397 followers in February 2021 to **782 in February 2023**, achieving the increased target KPI of 600 followers indicated in D5.2 and gradually becoming one of the most active accounts among similar initiatives.

³⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/blue-cloud-org/>

Page		Total engagements	Total posts
1	DOORS Black Sea	1,071	105
2	Blue-Cloud Org	1,006	111
3	Nautilus	560	58
4	Mission Atlantic	524	72
5	EUROFLEETS	412	52
6	EOSC Future	314	45
7	EOSC-Life	286	149
8	AqualNFRA	167	28
9	ENVRI community	12	2
10	iAtlantic	0	0

Figure 26 Comparison of total engagement for past 12 months with other similar projects

In particular, visibility on LinkedIn was enhanced by directly tagging participants, contributors, guests, speakers on specific posts, such as the Blue-Cloud Final Conference³⁷, allowing for more reach among professionals from across the marine and maritime sectors.

³⁷ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/blue-cloud-org_bluecloudfc-openscience-bluecloud2026-activity-7007014459982405632-ferW

Figure 27 Example of a popular LinkedIn post

3.2.3. YouTube

Over the second half of the project lifetime, YouTube has increasingly become a relevant channel for outreach. Since the 24 videos featured as of February 2022 in D5.2, the channel³⁸ has grown to **80 videos** as of the end of the project, **collecting a total of over 35k views through its lifetime**.

Videos have been arranged into thematic playlists³⁹, including:

- 19 videos in the webinar playlist - with also several joint ones with other initiatives.
- 10 videos in the tutorials playlist.
- 14 videos in the interviews playlist.
- 18 videos in the hackathon playlist.
- 3 videos from the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum 2020.

³⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/@BlueCloudorg/>

³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/@BlueCloudorg/playlists>

- 8 videos from the Blue-Cloud workshop “Improving the knowledge of our oceans and seas and bringing them closer to citizens”.

In particular, the most popular video produced by Blue-Cloud was the one realised to present the project in October 2021⁴⁰. The video was produced to serve as an introduction to all the main results available towards the second half of the project, including the core services and Virtual Labs.

The video was also advertised through a PPC campaign on YouTube, which was carried out between January and March 2022, contributing to attract **more than 25k views** and **118 new subscribers** to the Blue-Cloud YouTube channel. This content was also shown at the Blue-Cloud Final Conference.

Figure 28 Thumbnail of the Blue-Cloud promotional video

3.3. Zenodo community

The official Blue-Cloud Zenodo Community⁴¹ was opened in February 2021, connected to the Blue-Cloud Catalogue on D4Science⁴². The Community has gradually become a core element of the project’s online presence and will be maintained in Blue-Cloud 2026.

Project deliverables, documents, public presentations, downloadable and printable materials (such as posters and booklets) are collected on Zenodo and made available to the wider community. So far 73 items are available on Zenodo, of which 42 publications, 10 presentations, 6 posters, 5 datasets, 4 software.

⁴⁰ <https://youtu.be/3WLNQxKDAQ>

⁴¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities>

⁴² <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/catalogue-bluecloud>

3.4. Newsletters

Blue-Cloud Newsletters include details about upcoming and past events, as well as achievements and relevant messages for the Blue-Cloud community. Its content is shaped around the milestone results of the work plan, featuring comments and articles published on the Blue-Cloud website.

As of the end of December 2022, 26 newsletters were circulated (see Table 7) to an audience of more than 800 contacts from across the marine research, Open Science and blue economy communities. Topics included updates from the project, promotion of Blue-Cloud services and project events, such as thematic webinars introducing Virtual Labs, the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, as well as the evolution of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030.

The initial goal of the project was to send out quarterly newsletters, but these gradually became more frequent and one of the most successful channels of communication for the project. A percentage rate of open issues between 33 and 37 is good and shows interest in the content of the project.

In February 2023, the first newsletter issue branded as the follow-up project Blue-Cloud 2026 was officially launched.

N	Title	Date	Total opens (%)	Total clicks (%)
special issue	<u>All You Need To Know About The "Improving The Knowledge Of Our Oceans And Seas" Workshop, 5 February</u>	04.02.2020	70.8	43.1
special issue	<u>Thank You For Your Participation At The "Improving The Knowledge Of Our Oceans And Seas" Workshop</u>	14.02.2020	47.2	25
1	<u>Welcome To The Blue-Cloud Newsletter: Get To Know The Blue-Cloud Project And Read What They Say About Us</u>	14.05.2020	45	14
2	<u>Join Webinar 19 June 2020 Blue-Cloud Demonstrators - Helping Translate Marine Research Into Innovation For The Blue Economy</u>	09.06.2020	41.7	10,1
3	<u>Webinar Recording, Plankton Demonstrator, New Synergies & Much More</u>	25.06.2020	40.9	11.4
4	<u>Roadmap To 2030, Marine Environmental Indicators Demonstrator, New Webinars & Much More</u>	30.07.2020	42.3	12.4
5	<u>Join Us For The Webinar 25 September 2020 The European Research & Innovation Days Blue-Cloud Roadmap To 2030 & Much More</u>	21.09.2020	32.7	15.6
6	<u>Join Us Tomorrow 14 Oct For The New Webinar Have Your Say! On The Roadmap 2030 Events With Blue-Cloud & Much More</u>	13.10.2020	38	11.5
7	<u>Have Your Say On The Roadmap 2030 By 6 November The Next Webinar On Marine</u>	04.11.2020	37	7.5

N	Title	Date	Total opens (%)	Total clicks (%)
	Environmental Indicators Events & Much More			
8	Blue-Cloud Newsletter: Join Us On 4 December For The New Webinar "Marine Environmental Indicators"	02.12.2020	37.4	11.7
9	Our Season's Greetings Come With Latest News-->Synergies Overview, Save The Date For The Next Webinar In February & Much More	23.12.2020	33.6	9.2
10	Next Webinar 12.02 The First Of New Interviews' Series With Jean-Olivier Irisson - EcoTaxa First Results Of Roadmap & More	02.02.2021	36.5	8.8
11	The Public Workshop On 23 March, The Virtual Research Environments Explained, Next Events And Much More	05.03.2021	33.6	11.2
12	The Plankton Genomics Webinar 23.04 -> Join us! Workshop "Open Science for the Ocean" -> Read the Report Interviews' section Next Events & More	16.04.2021	31.3	9.8
13	All-Atlantic 2021 & The Blue-Cloud Workshop On 3 June The Recording Of The Webinar On Plankton Genomics The Thierry Carval Interview & Much More	27.05.2021	35.3	7.9
14	Help us shape the future of Blue-Cloud! Take the Survey The new Support Centre All-Atlantic 2021 Report & More	16.07.2021	30.9	5.2
15	Blue-Cloud Newsletter Contribute to the Open Consultation by 22 October Poster @ the EGI Conference The joint policy brief The Webinars & more	19.10.2021	34	5.7
16	Take part in the Blue-Cloud Hackathon and win prizes!	09.12.2021	33.6	9.6
17	The Blue-Cloud Hackathon 7-9 February & the Kick-off live event 17 January 2022 ready to start REGISTER NOW!	14.01.2022	39.6	6.1
18	Three teams awarded at the Blue-Cloud Hackathon The 1st of the new webinar series on 24 March Blue-Cloud included in the CORDIS synergy info pack	01.03.2022	34.7	9.4
19	Test the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and follow the Ocean Decade Laboratory	06.05.2022	31.9	7.5

N	Title	Date	Total opens (%)	Total clicks (%)
20	Blue-Cloud at the EU Green Week 2022	30.05.2022	30.9	4.3
21	Join Our Webinar On 20 June, Test The Aquaculture Monitor Virtual Lab	17.06.2022	31.4	5.9
22	How Are You Liking Blue-Cloud? Take Our Quick Survey!	07.09.2022	35	5.6
23	Blue-Cloud at the FAO Science and Innovation Forum 2022 + Wildlife Tracker for Oceans	07.10.2022	34.2	7.3
24	Blue-Cloud Final Conference in Brussels, 8 December 2022 - Register now!	19.10.2022	38.8	7.9
25	Blue-Cloud Final Conference, 8 December 2022 - Register By 1 December To Join Us In Brussels!	25.11.2022	39.3	6.7
26	Unlocking Open Science in support of the EU Green Deal - Insights from Blue-Cloud Final Event	22.12.2022	37.2	5.8
Average issues 1-26			36	8.7

Table 10 Blue-Cloud newsletters

3.5. Press Coverage

In the second reporting period M19-M42, the project has also experienced visibility with mentions both on general and specialised media outside of the consortium network, especially thanks to the Blue-Cloud Hackathon. Some examples can be found below:

Date	Title	Website	Audience	Link
26.07.2021	L'OceanTech, un domaine prometteur boudé par les investisseurs	Maddyness	Entrepreneurship and innovation	https://www.maddyness.com/2021/07/26/loceantec-h-un-domaine-prometteur-boude-par-les-investisseurs/
09.02.2022	Blue Cloud sees major growth with new 'Virtual Labs'	Science Business	Science	https://sciencebusiness.net/network-updates/photonics21-blue-cloud-sees-major-growth-new-virtual-labs
09.02.2022	Marine thematic EOSC Blue-Cloud sees major growth with new 'Virtual Labs'	EOSC Portal	Open Science	https://eosc-portal.eu/news/marine-thematic-eosc-blue-cloud-sees-major-growth-new-%E2%80%98virtual-labs%E2%80%99

Date	Title	Website	Audience	Link
18.02.2022	Oceanographers win €25.000 Blue-Cloud Hackathon prize	Utrecht University	Research and academia	https://www.uu.nl/en/news/oceanographers-win-eu25000-blue-cloud-hackathon-prize
21.02.2022	Blue-Cloud Hackathon winners help tackle ocean plastic	The Fish Site	Fisheries and aquaculture	https://thefishsite.com/articles/blue-cloud-hackathon-winners-help-tackle-ocean-plastic
21.02.2022	Innovative aquaculture prototype by RBI researchers awarded at the Blue-Cloud Hackathon	Ruđer Bošković Institute	Research and academia	https://www.irb.hr/eng/News/Innovative-aquaculture-prototype-by-RBI-researchers-awarded-at-the-Blue-Cloud-Hackathon
28.02.2022	D4Science & Blue-Cloud	Il Sole 24 Ore	Business and industry	https://minisiti.ilsole24ore.com/scenari_28febbraio_bis/scenari_28febbraio_bis.pdf
23.11.2022	Providing access to data resources & interoperable tools for open marine science and applications	AtlantECO	Ocean science	https://www.atlanteco.eu/post/providing-access-to-data-resources-interoperable-tools-for-open-marine-science-and-applications
16.02.2023	Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research	EOSC Future	Open Science	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646200

Table 11 Examples of articles featured on third party websites

3.6. Scientific papers

Date	Title	Published in	Authors	Link
28.04.2020	Distributed service-level agreement management with smart contracts and blockchain	Concurrency and Computation	Rafael Brundo Uriarte, Huan Zhou, Kyriakos Kritikos, Zeshun Shi, Zhiming Zhao, Rocco De Nicola	https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.5800

Date	Title	Published in	Authors	Link
09.10.2020	A Cost-Quality Beneficial Cell Selection Approach for Sparse Mobile Crowdsensing with Diverse Sensing Costs	IEEE Internet of Things (IoT) Journal	Zhu, Zhengqiu; Chen, Bin; Liu, Wenbin; Zhao, Yong; Liu, Zhong; Zhao, Zhiming	https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2020.3024833
06.10.2020	Reinforcing Fisheries Management through Semantic Data Integration	ERCIM News	Yannis Tzitzikas; Yannis Marketakis (FORTH-ICS)	https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en123/special/reinforcing-fisheries-management-through-semantic-data-integration
18.10.2020	Decentralized workflow management on software defined infrastructures	2020 IEEE World Congress on Services (SERVICES)	Wang, Yuandou; Zhao, Zhiming	https://doi.org/10.1109/SERVICES48979.2020.00059
11.11.2020	Elas4RDF: Multi-perspective Triple-Centered Keyword Search over RDF Using Elasticsearch	European Semantic Web Conference 2020	Giorgos Kadilierakis, Christos Nikas, Pavlos Fafalios, Panagiotis Papadakos & Yannis Tzitzikas	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-62327-2_21
13.01.2021	ReLock: a resilient two-phase locking RESTful transaction model	Service Oriented Computing and Applications	Luca Frosini, Pasquale Pagano, Leonardo Candela, Manuele Simi & Cinzia Bernardeschi	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11761-020-00311-z
04.03.2021	A Trustworthy Blockchain-based Decentralised Resource Management System in the Cloud	IEEE International Conference on Parallel and Distributed Systems (ICPADS)	Zhao, Zhiming; Rong, Chunming; Jaatun, Martin Gilje	https://doi.org/10.1109/ICPADS51040.2020.000086
18.03.2021	On the Evolution of Semantic Warehouses: The Case of Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries	Research Conference on Metadata and Semantics	Yannis Marketakis, Yannis Tzitzikas, Aureliano Gentile, Bracken van Niekerk & Marc Taconet	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-71903-6_26

Date	Title	Published in	Authors	Link
		Research MTSR		
30.06.2021	Building a Blockchain-based Decentralized Ecosystem for Cloud and Edge Computing: an ALLSTAR approach and empirical study	Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications	Huan Zhou, Zeshun Shi, Xue Ouyang & Zhiming Zhao	https://doi.org/10.1007/s12083-021-01198-z
01.09.2021	An Open Science approach to infer fishing activity pressure on stocks and biodiversity from vessel tracking data	Ecological Informatics	Gianpaolo Coro, Anton Ellenbroek, Pasquale Pagano	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoinf.2021.101384
22.11.2021	Knowledge sharing and discovery across heterogeneous research infrastructures	Open Research Europe	Siamak Farshidi, Xiaofeng Liao, Na Li, Doron Goldfarb, Barbara Magagna, Markus Stocker, Keith Jeffery, Peter Thijssen, Christian Pichot, Andreas Petzold, Zhiming Zhao	https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/1-68
10.03.2022	Virtual research environments co-creation: The D4Science experience	12th International Workshop on Science Gateways (IWSG 2020)	Massimiliano Assante, Leonardo Candela, Donatella Castelli, Roberto Cirillo, Gianpaolo Coro, Andrea Dell'Amico, Luca Frosini, Lucio Lelii, Marco Lettere, Francesco Mangiacrapa, Pasquale Pagano, Giancarlo Panichi, Tommaso Piccioli, Fabio Sinibaldi	https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6925
22.03.2022	A Decentralized Service Control Framework for	ESOC 2022: Service-Oriented and	Bram Hoogenkamp, Siamak Farshidi, Ruyue Xin, Zeshun Shi,	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04718-3_4

Date	Title	Published in	Authors	Link
	Decentralized Applications in Cloud Environments.	Cloud Computing	Peng Chen & Zhiming Zhao	
01.04.2022	Scaling Notebooks as Re-configurable Cloud Workflows	MIT Data Intelligence	Wang, Y., Koulouzis, S., Bianchi, R., Li, N., Shi, Y., Timmermans, J., Kissling, W.D., Zhao, Z.	https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00140
11.05.2022	An Adaptable Indexing Pipeline for Enriching Meta Information of Datasets from Heterogeneous Repositories	PAKDD 2022: Advances in Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining	Siamak Farshidi & Zhiming Zhao	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05936-0_37
17.05.2022	Notebook-as-a-VRE (NaaVRE): From private notebooks to a collaborative cloud virtual research environment.	Software: practice and experience	Zhiming Zhao, Spiros Koulouzis, Riccardo Bianchi, Siamak Farshidi, Zeshun Shi, Ruyue Xin, Yuandou Wang, Na Li, Yifang Shi, Joris Timmermans, W. Daniel Kissling	https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.3098
18.05.2022	A workflow for supporting the evolution requirements of RDF-based semantic warehouses	InderScience Publishers	Yannis Marketakis, Yannis Tzitzikas, Aureliano Gentile, Bracken Van Niekerk and Marc Taconet	https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMSO.2021.123044
22.08.2022	Spatiotemporal analysis of plankton drivers in the Belgian part of the North Sea (<i>to be accepted</i>)	Biogeosciences - Special issue: Towards an understanding and assessment of human impact on coastal marine environments	Viviana Otero, Steven Pint, Jonas Mortelmans, Klaas Deneudt, Maarten De Rijcke, Lennert Schepers, Patricia Cabrera, Koen Sabbe, Wim Vyverman, Michiel Vandegehuchte and Gert Everaert	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5575442

Date	Title	Published in	Authors	Link
01.11.2022	A Bayesian game-enhanced auction model for federated cloud services using blockchain	Future generation coputer system	Zeshun Shi, Huan Zhou, Cees de Laat, Zhiming Zhao	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2022.05.017
07.2022	Scaling Notebooks as Re-configurable Cloud Workflows	CEUR Workshop proceedings	Y. Marketakis, Y. Tzitzikas, A. Gentile, B. Van Niekerk, and Marc Taconet	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3293/paper53.pdf

3.7. Special issue Journal

Blue-Cloud has engaged with the **International Journal of Data Science and Analytics** to release a special issue dedicated to Blue-Cloud’s results. While the issue is open to all, expected submissions should come from both Blue-Cloud and Blue-Cloud 2026 partners. The call for submission will open on 1st of September 2023 and will stay open up to March 2024.

Guest editors will include: Hongsheng Bi, Center for Environmental Science, University of Maryland, College Park Cambridge, United States and Blue-Cloud partners Leonardo Candela, Institute of Information Science and Technologies - National Research Council of Italy, Pisa, Italy; Pasquale Pagano, Institute of Information Science and Technologies - National Research Council of Italy, Pisa, Italy; Dick Schaap, MARIS, Nootdorp, The Netherlands.

Aims

Data Science and AI play increasingly critical roles in Marine Science observation, operation and sustainable utilization. This special issue aims for publishing up-to-date high-quality research and innovation results in all areas related to AI, data science, and scientific workflows in marine science. Contributions promoting Open Science and FAIRness are particularly encouraged.

Topics

All topics related to AI, Data Science, and Scientific Workflows including statistical and mathematical modelling, knowledge representation and discovery, machine learning, deep learning, simulation and visualization, and innovative tasks composition for the acquisition, integration, reduction, visualization, and publication of data in marine-related application contexts are welcome.

Papers may address the interdisciplinary vision, position, review and significant theoretical and practical contributions to synergize AI, Data Science and machine/deep learning with marine science and to innovate new-generation systems and services. This includes but is not limited to new theoretical and technical advancements as well as novel and significant real-world applications. Open Science and FAIRness approaches deserve a special mention. Survey, position and vision papers are also welcome.

3.8. Communication materials (digital and print)

Concerning communication materials, besides the logo, a complete communication toolkit⁴³ was made available to the consortium. Over the months, a series of materials for digital use and for printing were created by Trust-IT and COMMpla to promote Blue-Cloud at physical and online events. Examples are described in the table below.

Type	Produced by M41
Posters	6 posters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Blue-Cloud Poster 70x100 ○ Poster EOSC-hub Week 2020 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5534128 ○ Poster EMODnet Conference 2021 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5525003 ○ Poster EGI Conference 2021 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5584799 ○ Poster June 2022 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6655327 ○ Poster September 2022 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7101547
Flyers	1 flyer: Blue-Cloud Flyer A5
Virtual Lab factsheets (flyers)	8 Factsheets with information about thematic services for users. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Five about the Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs • Three about the winning teams of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon Printed for the Blue-Cloud Final Conference Link to collection https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663960
Rollup banner	2 rollup banners: Kick-off meeting Blue-Cloud Roll-up Banner Final Conference
Press Releases	1 Press release: Launch of Blue-Cloud, a ground-breaking project piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy - Dec 2019
PPT template	1 template: Blue-Cloud PPT Template
Videos	80 videos (more info under section 3.2 Social media)
Giveaways	Pens and notepads
Blue-Cloud Roadmap Executive Summary	A summary of the Strategic Roadmap to 2030, containing its main elements and infographics. Printed for the Blue-Cloud Final Conference Link https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377985
Blue-Cloud Synergy collection	Information about the different synergies established by Blue-Cloud over its lifetime, describing joint activities and impact. https://blue-cloud.org/synergies

⁴³ <https://www.blue-cloud.org/communications-kit>

Type	Produced by M41
EOSC in Practice stories	<p>Stories created in collaboration with the EOSC Future project</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Discovery and Access Service https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7646200 • Virtual Research Environment to be published in Q2 2023

Table 12 Blue-Cloud communication materials by M41

3.9. Horizon Results Booster activity

The Horizon Results Booster (HRB) is a package of specialised services launched in 2020 by the European Commission to help projects funded in Framework Programmes maximise the impact of their results and amplify the added value of their activities.

The HRB supports projects which are looking to collaborate on joint efforts with other ones working on similar topics, establishing project groups that can exploit each other's networks and join forces for the creation of materials.

In late 2020, Blue-Cloud joined a 10-project-strong group called "Nourishing Blue Economy, Sharing Ocean Knowledge" led by EuroSea, in the context of the HRB, focussing on supporting excellence in marine research, policies & partnerships, to strengthen its network and reach out to more stakeholders across Europe and beyond.

This collaboration brought several of the projects involved to take part in the 2nd EuroSea Annual Event in January 2021, as well as to the definition of shared goals and priorities. Thanks to the HRB, the project group also produced a joint video⁴⁴ and a flyer⁴⁵ to help promote the vision and key results to a broader audience.

The main output of this collaboration was a joint policy brief, published on 15 October 2021, focusing on Nourishing blue economy and sharing data knowledge. **It was viewed 571 and downloaded 406 times on Zenodo**⁴⁶. The policy brief was also presented at the joint workshop held at EMD 2022 in Ravenna, Italy.

Figure 29 Promotional image for the joint policy brief in HRB

⁴⁴ <https://youtu.be/7lj3xYdXLFi>

⁴⁵ <https://data.d4science.net/ZsQC>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5576120>

4. Events

4.1. Blue-Cloud Workshops

Blue-Cloud organised six workshops, either stand-alone or co-located with other conferences, to engage with different stakeholders, including marine data infrastructures, research infrastructures and e-infrastructures, Policy Makers, blue economy industry, researchers & scientists, ICT industry, producers, distributors and users of marine data and representatives of other European initiatives (see table 11). The organisation of these events was crucial to engage with larger audiences and to promote both technical developments of Blue-Cloud services, as well as to collect inputs for the Blue-Cloud Roadmap and establish new synergies.

The workshops organised in collaboration with other “blue initiatives and organisations”, helped spread further the word about Blue-Cloud, collecting insights that would support not only the development of Blue-Cloud services, but also to contribute to the bigger picture in supporting the growth of the blue economy and the protection of marine environments. Altogether, the events provided a golden opportunity for Blue-Cloud to join key initiatives in the international blue economy landscape.

Date	Event title & Location	Co-organisers	Goal	Participants
05.02.2020	Improving the knowledge of our oceans and seas and bringing them closer to citizens (Brussels, Belgium)	AANChOR and AORAC-SA projects and the AtlantOS program	Contribute to the implementation of the Galway and the Belém Statements by better understanding the international data/e-infrastructure landscape and the needed federation efforts to accelerate the establishment of a global “Blue-Cloud” able to effectively and efficiently bring data at the service of society.	110
03.06.2021	Towards an All-Atlantic Data Space for the Ocean (Online)	AANChOR, the G7 Future of the Seas and Oceans Initiative, iAtlantic and AtlantECO	Debate about EU and international initiatives working to harmonize and facilitate data sharing across the Atlantic, and provide demonstrations of available tools, training, and the latest open science ‘blue cloud’ technologies to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.	184
23.03.2021	Open Science for the Ocean: meet Blue-Cloud Demonstrators (Online)		Demonstrate how the Blue-Cloud is combining distributed marine data and computing resources with analytical tools to deliver services supporting marine	208

Date	Event title & Location	Co-organisers	Goal	Participants
			research on better understanding & managing the many aspects of ocean sustainability and demonstrating the potential of open science in the marine domain. The five dedicated Blue-Cloud demonstrators were presented and initial reflections on the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030 were shared.	
14.12.2021	Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond (Online)	AANChOR	Provide more information about the Blue-Cloud Hackathon , taking place in February 2022, where teams of marine researchers can test the Blue-Cloud technical framework under four different thematic challenges and also win prizes for working on their solutions.	101
19.05.2022	Ocean observations, marine data and services for the European Green Deal (Ravenna, Italy, EMD 2022)	EuroSea and EMODnet	Discuss the value of a coordinated, sustained, and fit-for-purpose ocean observing and information system serving policy, industry, and wider society, as well as opportunities, gaps, and priorities to reach the European Green Deal objectives	80
17.11.2022	Blue-Cloud Open Science platform as a model for a sustainable Data federation in EOSC: workshop at the EOSC Symposium 2022 (Prague, Czech Republic, EOSC Symposium 2022)		Debate about Blue-Cloud Data federation model and its tangible implementation via use cases. A panel of experts from the EOSC Sustainability Task Force, marine data and service providers, and disciplinary communities discussed why and how to continue sustaining data federation practices in EOSC.	35

Table 13 Blue-Cloud workshops

Figure 30 Visuals from Blue-Cloud workshops

4.2. Blue-Cloud Hackathon

The [Blue-Cloud Hackathon](#) took place from 7-9 February 2022, featuring 149 participants from 73 countries that led the creation of 32 teams, which were mentored by 27 members from Blue-Cloud consortium. From the 32 initial teams, a total of 23 completed the challenge, representing 111 participants. Amongst these 23 Teams, 10 were invited to defend their ideas during a “Pitching & Award Live Event”, as finalists.

Before the Hackathon, a [kick-off live event](#) was organised on 17th January 2022, which provided insights about the hackathon objectives & challenges, what participants could expect, as well as a generic overview of the topics and challenges to be addressed.

After the hackathon, a [Pitching & Award Live Event](#) was organised, counting with over 130 participants, to introduce the finalist teams of the hackathon. At this event, the teams who had the chance to present short video-pitches of their ideas developed during the hackathon. A panel of external expert judges were onboarded to evaluate the ideas and submissions of the teams, interact with participants and decide which ones deserved the 1st, 2nd and 3rd place awards. In addition, a "Blue Skies Award" was granted by popular vote. The three winning teams were awarded with funding and two dedicated coaching sessions to further develop, boost and promote the uptake of their solutions. Up to 2 members of each team were invited to take part in the final Blue-Cloud conference at the end of the project, with their travel costs covered.

Figure 31 Branding for the Blue-Cloud Hackathon

Regarding the participants, data scientists and marine researchers made up about two thirds of the hackathon participants. There was also a considerable representation from students of both marine and computer science (about 20%), which is a promising signal for future talent and skills in support of Ocean research and the Blue Economy. The Blue-Cloud Hackathon was the first hackathon experience for almost half of the participants. Roughly one third had already attended similar events, while the rest could be considered hackathon “veterans”.

Figure 32 Infographic with Blue-Cloud hackathon statistics

The Blue-Cloud Hackathon was a success, surpassing the KPI of 60 participants (reaching 149 participants) from different user communities. It was also an opportunity for the Blue-Cloud consortium to see the services developed in the project “in action”, welcoming a wide and diverse community of users to test them intensively.

Furthermore, the virtual hackathon was used to inform the Blue-Cloud Roadmap, providing ideas for user-focused applications of blue data services.

4.3. Blue-Cloud Final Conference

On the 8th of December 2022, Blue-Cloud stakeholders gathered in Brussels for the **final conference**, welcoming over 170 representatives from the **European Parliament, the European Commission DG RTD, the EOSC governance, the EU Digital Twin of the Ocean initiatives as well as researchers and end users from the European marine research community**. The event provided the perfect opportunity to learn about the main achievements and the road ahead of this key component of the EU “Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative” and to officially introduce the new project that will ensure follow-up of Blue-Cloud achievements until 2026.

The Final conference was also the perfect scene to launch the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030, which defines Strategic Goals and a comprehensive Action Plan to drive future developments towards delivering Blue-Cloud’s Mission 2030, working around 5 strategic paths of action. **Julia Vera**, Seascope

Belgium, presented the Blue-Cloud roadmap, which has been co-designed with the wider marine and ICT community via extensive stakeholder consultations, workshops, online surveys, targeted interviews, and open feedback sessions. The Roadmap executive summary is available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377985>

The event was closed with the official announcement of the start of the follow-up Horizon Europe project **Blue-Cloud 2026** in January 2023. The new initiative continues and expands on the work set by Blue-Cloud by adding more data providers, increasing the number of scientific demonstrators, introducing new analytical services and data products, and launching a Training Academy to boost knowledge sharing and ocean literacy across researchers working in the open science and Digital Twin of the Ocean landscapes.

A [3-minute video](#) with highlights of the conference was produced, along with a [dedicated piece of news](#).

Figure 33 Promotional image and group photo of the Final Conference

4.4. Blue-Cloud at third-party events

During the whole project timeframe, Blue-Cloud has actively participated in +60 events, from Marine, Blue Economy and Earth Sciences, Open Science and Technical fields, as illustrated in Table 13, clearly surpassing the KPI of 50+ events by the end of the project. The continuous promotion of Blue-Cloud ensured a global visibility, in Europe and beyond.

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
1	SIST workshop – November 2019	Toulouse, France	Data Managers	Presentation & short workshop
2	Open Science Conference – November 2019	Montpellier, France	Data Managers	Presentation
3	EOSC Symposium – November 2019	Budapest, Hungary	Research & Academia, Business & industry, EOSC projects, EU infrastructures and Research Infrastructures, policy makers, funding agencies, industry representatives, HPC centers, SDOs, citizen scientists, publishers, data service providers.	1 presentation and 2 panels

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
4	EuroSea kick-off meeting – November 2019	Brussels, Belgium	Professionals of ocean observation and forecasting	Presentation
5	General Assembly of the EuroMarine Network – January 2020	Piran, Slovenia	Ocean research network, small and large laboratories of research and academic organisations	Presentation
6	Ocean Decade Med Sea workshop – January 2020	Venice, Italy	Mediterranean Sea stakeholders	Presentation
7	ENVRI Week – February 2020	Dresden, Germany	Environmental Research Infrastructures and eInfrastructures	Poster Presentation
8	All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum – February 2020	Brussels, Belgium	Marine scientists, policy makers working on the Atlantic Ocean	Presentation & Workshop
9	EMSO Conference – February 2020	Athens, Greece	Marine researchers, engineers, and representatives of industry, Institutions, Research Infrastructures and Funding Agencies.	Presentation
10	PHIDIAS HPC Webinar: Building a prototype for Earth Science Data and HPC Services – February 2020	Webinar	HPC community, Big data scientists, Earth observation researchers, Marine life experts, Research and academies	Presentation
11	Advancing Data Stewardship Workshop – February 2020	Oostend, Belgium	Environmental and Life Science Research Infrastructures	Presentation
12	Open Belgium – March 2020	Hasselt, Belgium	industry, research, government and citizen stakeholders	Presentation
13	EGU – May 2020	Online	Scientists, researchers and experts in all fields of geoscience	Presentation
14	NEAC workshop in IEEE CCGrid 2020 – May 2020	Online	Network communications researchers	Paper presentation
15	EOSC-hub Week – M19ay 2020	Online	Research & Academia, Business & industry, EOSC projects, EU eInfrastructures and Research Infrastructures, policy makers, funding agencies, industry representatives, HPC centers, SDOs, citizen scientists, publishers, data service providers	Poster presentation

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
16	GFCM Virtual Seminar on Aquaculture and Marine Spatial Planning – June 2020	Online	Aquaculture stakeholders	Presentation
17	WEBINAR: Boosting the use of cloud services for marine data management, services and processing – June 2020	Online	Big Data and HPC communities, Scientific Communities, ocean and marine initiative and projects, Research infrastructure staff, repository managers	Presentation
18	European Research & Innovation Days 2020 – September 2020	Online	Policy makers, researchers, entrepreneurs and the public	Panel
19	ESA Phi week – September 2020	Online	Scientists, political and economic decision makers involved in AI, Earth Science and Cloud computing	Presentation
20	SIST 2020 – September 2020	Online	Data Managers Network	Presentation
21	Sea Tech Week 2020 – October 2020	Online	Ocean and genomic observation data, open access to marine data and oceans monitoring professionals	Presentation
22	IODE: International Data Sharing Workshop for Non-UN IGOs, Global and Regional Organizations and Projects, NGOs and Private Sector – October 2020	Online	Oceanographic data professionals	Panel
23	EMB Big Data in Marine Science – October 2020	Online	Professionals from big data, digitalization and artificial intelligence in marine science	Presentation
24	SeaDataCloud Plenary Group meeting – October 2020	Online	Ocean and marine data management experts	Presentation
25	Realising the European Open Science Cloud – November 2020	Online	Social science and humanities researchers, data experts, research funders, policymakers, research infrastructures, service providers, research libraries and archives, the EOSC Ecosystem, and ESFRI Cluster projects	Virtual stand

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
26	Online courses on the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in the establishment of Allocated Zones for Aquaculture – November 2020	Online	Aquaculture and marine spatial planning professionals	Presentation
27	16th Working Party on Data Collection and Statistics (WPDCS16) – November 2020	Online	Data Collection and Statistics experts from Indian Tuna Ocean	Presentation
29	IEEE CloudCom conference 2020 – December 2020	Online	Cloud Computing professionals	Presentation
30	EuroSea Annual Event - January 2021	Online	EuroSea consortium	Presentation
31	Copernicus Land, Marine & Coastal Workshop - March 2021	Online	Marine representatives of the public, commercial and scientific communities	Presentation
32	IMDIS 2021 - April 2021	Online	Marine and oceanographic data communities	Presentation
33	Blue Research Innovation Days - April 2021	Online	Researchers, Industry and SMEs representatives, scientists, students, start-up owners active in aquaculture, fisheries, marine, ocean, underwater, socioeconomics and ICT sector	Joint-Workshop
34	9th EuroGOOS International Conference - May 2021	Online	Operational oceanography professionals	Presentation
35	The 52nd International Liège colloquium on ocean dynamics - May 2021	Online	Scientists, stakeholders and SMEs	Presentation
36	All-Atlantic Data & Policy Forum - May 2021	Online	Policy Makers from All Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and Innovation	Panel
37	EMODnet Open Conference and Jamboree 2021 - June 2021	Online	Industry, research, policy and in civil society.	Poster & Video

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
38	EOSC Symposium 2021 - June 2021	Online	Ministries, policy makers, research organisations, service providers, research infrastructures and research communities across Europe and beyond	Lightning talk
39	Artificial intelligence for a digital blue planet forum agenda - June 2021	Online	Data scientists, analysts and researchers from marine research institutions and universities around the world	Presentation
40	Navigating the Future V as inspiration and direction for marine science in the Ocean Decade - August 2021	Online	Policy Makers from marine science	Presentation
41	Open Science FAIR 2021 - September 2021	Online	Open science communities and services	Workshop & Lightning talk
42	EGI Conference 2021 - October 2021	Online	Researchers & Data Scientists	Poster
43	LifeWatch Biodiversity Day 2021 - October 2021	Online	Citizens, policy and industry	Presentation
44	International Ocean Data Conference 2022 - The Data We Need for the Ocean We Want - February 2022	Sopot, Poland	Data Managers & Policy Makers	Presentation
45	Oceanology International 2022 - March 2022	London, UK	World's marine science and ocean technology communities	Poster
46	Ocean Decade Laboratory satellite activity - May 2022	Online	Worldwide Ocean Experts	Presentation
47	European Maritime Day 2022 - May 2022	Ravenna, Italy	Professionals from businesses, governments, public institutions, NGOs and academia	Workshop
48	All-Atlantic Data 2030 - African Data Infrastructures & Stakeholders - May 2022	Online	Policy Makers & Researchers across Atlantic	Presentation

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
49	EU Green Week 2022 - May 2022	Online	Stakeholders and interested citizens on zero pollution and toxic-free environment.	Presentation
50	TNC 2022 - June 2022	Trieste, Italy	Research and education networking professionals	Poster
51	ESOF 2022 - July 2022	Leiden, Netherlands	Interdisciplinary scientific communities	Poster
52	EGI Conference - September 2022	Prague, Czechia	Researchers & Data Scientists	Poster & Presentation
53	EU R&I Days 2022	Online	Policy Makers, researchers, entrepreneurs and the public to debate and shape the future of research and innovation in Europe and beyond	Presentation
54	MetroSea 2022 - October 2022	Milazzo, Italy	Professionals from developing instrumentation and measurement methods for the sea	Presentation
55	FAO Science and Innovation Forum - October 2022	Online	Scientists and Policy Makers	Presentation
56	Ocean Best Practices System VI - October 2022	Online	Researchers & Data Managers	Presentation
57	Marblue 2022 - October 2022	Constanta, Romania	Scientists and Policy Makers	Presentation
58	EOSC Symposium - November 2022	Prague, Czechia	Ministries, policy makers, research organisations, service providers, research infrastructures and research communities across Europe and beyond	Workshop
59	Eurofleets+ Marine Research Infrastructures Management Workshop - November 2022	Tallinn, Estonia	Marine Scientists and Marine science related staff	Workshop
60	Atlantic Stakeholder Platform Conference - December 2022	Online	Policy Makers and scientists	Workshop
61	Ocean Hackathon 2022 - December 2022	Online	Researchers from marine landscape	Hackathon
62	From data interoperability to data	Online	Aquaculture data managers	Workshop

N°	Event	Location	Audience	Activity
	spaces in the aquaculture domain- February 2023			

Table 14 Blue-Cloud presence at third-party events

5. COVID-19 Contingency Plans

Compared to the first reporting period, travel and event restrictions linked to the COVID-19 pandemic had different effects on project outreach activities. While M19-M30 saw a continuation of online-only meetings and events, things gradually changed in M31-M42.

As hinted in the Events section, this meant an expected decrease in the average number of participants in webinars over the months that saw, on the other hand, more possibilities for physical events and meetings. This trend started slowly with participation in key happenings like the International Ocean Data Conference 2022 and Oceanology International 2022, up to the first major physical workshop organised by Blue-Cloud and other initiatives at the European Maritime Day 2022 after long months of online activities.

This gradual change in the material conditions surrounding the project accompanied the evolution of communications activities – and project management in general – towards the successful organisation of the Final Conference as a hybrid event, paving the way for Blue-Cloud 2026.

6. Key Performance Indicators Targets Achieved

The table below summarises the status of communication and engagement KPIs to date as compared with targets. As the table shows, the results of Blue-Cloud’s intensive communication and dissemination activities has led to largely exceed the planned targets.

Topic	Results by M41	Target KPI by end of project
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visitors 44.576 ● Sessions 55.394 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Visitors 13.200 ● Sessions 28.800
Social media community	Total of 2400 members, more specifically: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Twitter: 1456 followers, 1,079,200 impressions, 1000+ tweets ● LinkedIn: 782 followers & 74,216 impressions ● YouTube: 36 videos & 900 average views 	Total of 2.000 members, more specifically: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Twitter: 1.000 followers, 700.000 impressions, 700 tweets ● LinkedIn: 200 followers & 100.000 impressions ● YouTube: 6 videos & 500 views per video
Website content customised to each Blue-Cloud target stakeholder	10 interviews and 32 blog post/articles Authors and guests from Italy, Netherlands, Ecuador, Spain, France, Germany, United Kingdom, Belgium, Croatia, Canada	30 interviews/blog pieces about different stakeholder groups from at least 10 different countries

Topic	Results by M41	Target KPI by end of project
Presence at third party events	60+ third party events	50+ third party physical and virtual events
Communication materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 9 flyers ● 6 posters ● 2 rollup banners ● 60+ presentations (note: considering the presence at 3rd-party events) ● 36 videos ● 2 give-aways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 4 fliers ● 4 posters ● 2 rollup banners ● 50 presentations ● 6 videos ● 2 give-aways
Newsletters	26	1 newsletter every 3 months, total of 12 newsletters
Virtual Hackathon	149 participants	By M28, with at least 60 participants
Synergies with European and international initiatives	22	Establish 10 new synergies documented via fact sheets
Profiled Dissemination database	1.830+ individual contacts	2,000 qualified contacts at the end of the project
Blue-Cloud Open Workshops	6 workshops, 120 avg participants	2 workshops by M14 and M22, with at least 50 participants.
Blue-Cloud roadmap workshops	3 workshops	3 workshops by M14, M22 and M34.
Blue-Cloud final event	Held in December 2022	1 event by M34 with at least 100 participants and a post-event report
Webinars	11 webinars, 53.8 avg viewers	10 webinars, with at least 30 participants each

Table 15 Target KPIs and achievements

7. Conclusions

This document summarises the main achievements of the Blue-Cloud project in terms of communication, dissemination and engagement, built on an increasingly strong network of partners, initiatives, and individuals committed to raising awareness and stimulating uptake of the Open Science approach and solutions developed and implemented by Blue-Cloud.

The diverse range of activities presented in this deliverable contributed to expanding the community in terms of outreach as well as of active users on the platform. The February 2022 Blue-Cloud Hackathon deserves a particular mention, as it was the first real chance for large amounts of users to test the Blue-Cloud framework, exploit its possibilities, and share constructive feedback for its improvement.

Thanks to consistent dialogue and presence at key events, Blue-Cloud also went on to become one of the most advanced projects in the EOSC community under Horizon 2020, consolidating interactions and collaborations across the board – including with leading initiatives such as EOSC Future and the EOSC Association Task Forces. The follow-up project Blue-Cloud 2026 under Horizon Europe is part of an exciting new round of INFRAEOSC projects, which will contribute to further develop and promote the European Open Science Cloud in scientific communities.

In addition, through its synergies and the visibility achieved through its lifetime, Blue-Cloud has also become a relevant actor in the new Digital Twin Ocean ecosystem, not only for its technical solutions, but also as an example of best practices for transnational and cross-disciplinary collaboration for ocean science.

Lessons learned on communication and dissemination activities during Blue-Cloud are precious for the follow-up Blue-Cloud 2026 and have already generated new ideas, such as the Blue-Cloud Training Academy, which will be implemented as part of the new Horizon Europe project.